

A Study on Emotional Maturity of High School Students

KEYWORDS

Emotional Maturity, Private high school students, Emotions, Behaviour

N.Subramanian

Ph.D. scholar, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Department of Education, Tirunelveli – 627012, Tamilnadu.

Dr.A.Veliappan

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli – 627012, Tamilnadu.

ABSTRACT *The emotional development of high students is the foundation for their cognitive development. Emotional support and secure relationships build a student's self confidence and the ability to function as a member of a group. So the investigator took the study "A study on Emotional Maturity of high school students". The objective of the study was to find out whether there is any significant difference in Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to gender and type of school. A descriptive survey method was adopted by the investigator to conduct this study. The investigator used the stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample. The investigator selected 335 high school students from Tenkasi Taluk. The tool used in the study was Emotional Maturity Scale by Yasvir Singh and Magesh Bharagava (1990). The investigator found that the high school boys and private high school students are emotionally matured.*

Significance of the Study

The Emotional maturity varies from child to child and culture to culture. Neglect of the emotional lives of children impacts on their intellectual lives and achievements as emotions are critical to the learning process and to the full development of the individual and to society. Learning to balance negative emotions with thoughts and actions that create positive emotions is a lifelong task and a difficult challenge to young teens. To attain emotional "maturity" they need to hone their control over socially discouraged emotions and express emotions in a more acceptable manner. An environment that allows for the range of emotions that kids experience will enhance self-acceptance and propel the maturity process forward. The emotional education debate includes big questions like, why do we need to teach children about emotions in school at all, and how should such teachings be implemented. Schools are torn between taking responsibility for the emotional education of its students, and with it the liability when things don't go as planned, and leaving it as it is today up to the parents. Signs of the deficiency in emotional maturity can be seen in violent incidents. Children who gained more insight into their emotional lives, were better able to cope with distress and anxiety, to the extent that they gained insight into the causes of those emotions (Harris, 1989). On the one hand, schools are designed to keep students busy learning about the outer world and not about themselves. On the other hand, families are not helping. They are either disintegrating, they can't afford to waste time listening to 'teenage issues', or they just don't know how to handle the complexity of issues involved. With this background the investigator made a study on emotional maturity of high school students.

Objectives of the Study

- To find out the level of Emotional Maturity of high school students with regard to gender and type of school.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between male and female high school students in their Emotional Maturity.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference among government, aided and unaided high school students in their Emotional Maturity.

Null Hypotheses

There is no significant difference between male and female high school students in their emotional maturity.

There is no significant difference among government, aided and unaided high school students in their emotional maturity.

Method

A descriptive survey method was adopted by the investigator to conduct this study.

Sample

The investigator used the stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample. The investigator selected 335 high school students from Tenkasi Taluk.

Tools Used for the Present Study

Emotional Maturity Scale developed by Yasvir Singh and Magesh Bharagava (1990).

Statistical Techniques Used

Percentage analysis, t-test, F- test and Scheffe test.

Analysis of Data

Table 1.01

Level of Emotional Maturity of high school students with regard to gender and type of school

Variable	Background Variable		Low		Average		High	
			Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Emotional Maturity	Gender	Male	39	29.1	61	45.5	34	25.4
		Female	45	22.4	106	52.7	50	24.9
	Type of School	Govt	27	18.9	76	53.1	40	28.0
		Aided	48	34.0	60	42.6	33	23.4
		Private	10	19.6	26	51.0	15	29.4

From the above table it is clear that more than one-third of high school students have average level of emotional maturity with regard to the gender and type of school.

Null Hypothesis: 1

There is no significant difference in Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to gender.

Table 1.02
t-test showing the significant difference in Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to gender

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't' value	Remarks
Emotional Maturity	Male	134	48.6716	36.99498	3.190	S
	Female	201	36.0249	34.54988		

(t=1.96 at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from the above table that, the calculated t-value (3.190) is greater than table value (1.96) for df (333) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant difference in emotional maturity of high school students with respect to gender. The mean response given by high school boys with respect to emotional maturity(48.67) is higher than the mean scores of high school girls(36.02).

Null Hypothesis: 2

There is no significant difference in emotional maturity of high school students with respect to type of school.

Table – 1.03

The F - test showing the significant difference in emotional maturity of high school students with respect to type of school						
Variable	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Calculated 'F' value	Remarks
Emotional Maturity	Between Groups	1626.131	2	813.065	4.701	S
	Within Groups	57425.847	332	172.969		
	Total	59051.978	334			

(F= 3.00 at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'F' value (4.701) is greater than the table value (3.00) for df(2,332) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus there is significant difference in emotional maturity of high school students with respect to type of school.

Table – 1.04

Scheffe test showing the mean difference in Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to type of school

Mean Value of Emotional Maturity			Result
Government	Aided	Private	
64.6012	67.2067	-	
-	67.2067	71.0390	
64.6012	-	71.0390	*

(* indicates that significant difference is present)

The Scheffe test from the above table indicates that the government and high school students differ significantly in their emotional maturity. The mean value of private high school students is greater than the government high school students.

Findings and Interpretations

From descriptive analysis, the investigator found that 25.4%

and 24.9% of high school girls and boys had high level of emotional maturity respectively. And also 28% of government high school students had high level of emotional maturity, while 23.4% of high school students and 29.4% of high school students had high level of emotional maturity.

From the t-test the investigator found that the high school boys have greater emotional maturity than the high school girls. It may be due to the fact that in our society gender role socialization practices differ for girls and boys. Girls are reared to be sensitive and expressive and they express their emotions very quickly whereas boys are not like that. Generally boys are not express vulnerable emotions such as fear, sadness, hurt, or attachment to another person. Young girls are more likely to struggle with higher levels of emotional problems and less emotional well-being than boys. Girls are more likely to experience emotional problems like feeling nervous, frustrated and helpless when they face problems. But the boys easily face their problems without any emotional problems.

There is significant difference in Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to type of school. The private high school students are emotionally matured than the government high school students. The reasons may be that the private schools may pay more attention to give proper counseling to promote sound social and psychological dispositions among their students. In private schools, most of the student's parents are well educated. It is also an important factor in the development of their emotional maturity.

Conclusion

Children's responses to the different feelings they experience every day have a major impact on their choices, their behaviour, and on how well they cope and enjoy life. Emotional development involves learning what feelings and emotions are, understanding how and why they happen, recognising one's own feelings and those of others, and developing effective ways of managing them. As children grow and are exposed to different situations their emotional lives also become more complex. Developing skills for managing a range of emotions is therefore very important for their emotional wellbeing. In this study, the investigator found that the high school boys are emotionally stable. Even if gender differences do exist in various spheres of life and even if inherent natural instincts cannot be overlooked, an effort can be made to create an environment for high school students of both sexes to give equal opportunities and freedom to identify and verbalize their feelings, as well as to read the emotional signals from other children and adults. Parents at home and teachers at school always play a major role in influencing and developing emotional maturity. Both the parents and teachers should accept emotional responses as legitimate without any sex discrimination. They may channelise their children's energy into constructive dimension. Most educational institutions, schools and colleges emphasize the thinking aspect, or cognition. Less attention is paid to the emotional aspects. Yet, emotions are important as they play a vital part in learning, and can help or hinder a child's academic commitment and success in school. Positive emotions directly relate to interest and self-motivation, which drive the attitudes critical for acquiring knowledge; negative emotions like depression are linked to the converse. Emotional development is important, and both the home and school environments are critical not just for good grades but also in nurturing success and happiness in life.

REFERENCE

Charles E Skinner(2009), Educational Psychology, Prentice Hall of India Pvt Limited, New Delhi, 2009: 249. | Greenberg, M. T., Kusch, C., & Mihalic, S. F. (1998), Blueprints for violence prevention, book 10: Promoting alternative thinking strategies (PATHS). Boulder, CO: Center for the Study and Prevention of Violence. | Harris, P. L. (1989). Children and emotion. Cambridge University Press, New York. | Mangal.S.K., Advanced Educational Psychology, Ashok K.Ghosu, New Delhi, 2007;314-318. | Menninger CW (1999). Emotional Maturity. New York: Hickman Associates. | Singh,Y., & Bhargava, M (1990), Manual for Emotional Maturity Scale, National Psychological corporation, Agra. | Subbarayan and G. Visvanathan(2011), "Study on Emotional Maturity of College Students", Recent Research in Science and Technology, Vol. 3, No.1: 153-155. |